

Cross-sectional analysis of stress and Dietary pattern among adults

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to assess prevalence of Stress in young adults and to ascertain the relation with socio-demographic characteristics and dietary habits. Cross-sectional survey was conducted in 2024-2025 in (Gurugram) India. The analytic sample included (n=1000) young adults (52.6% male and 47.4% female) aged 18-35 years. The Cohen Perceived stress scale (PSS) was used to measure the individual depressive state. Dietary habits assessed using a self-constructed questionnaire validated through expert reviews. The relation between stress, dietary habits and socio-demographic variables were studied using Karl Pearson correlation, ANOVA and student t test. A significant number of the participating young adults were male (52.6%), with the majority aged between 26-30 years (43.2%). majority of participants resided in nuclear families (77.4%), and the highest representation was in the high-income category (39.2%). Most participants were married (59.4%). Among them, 34.4% had a BMI that categorized them as overweight, with a higher incidence in male participants (18.2%) compared to female participants (16.8%). The majority of participants reported moderate stress levels (49.8%). The results comparing stress and dietary habits scores with sociodemographic factors indicated that males and those in the high-income group aged 31-35 were under significant stress. Women tended to adopt healthier dietary patterns, while the 26-30 age group made healthier food choices, and middle-income individuals showed better dietary patterns. Correlation analysis showed a significant negative correlation between poor dietary choices and stress among young working adults ($r=-0.354$, $p < 0.001$). The majority of young adults were overweight with moderate stress and had average dietary habits. stress was associated with poorer dietary habits among young adults.

Keywords: Stress, dietary pattern, dietary habits, young adults

INTRODUCTION

"Stress" has been termed the "Health Epidemic of the 21st Century". It is defined as a mental state of tension or anxiety triggered by challenging or demanding situations. The effects of stress on our emotional and physical health can be extremely harmful. (WHO). Hans Selye, often called the "Father of Stress," remarked, "Stress is the nonspecific response of the body to any demand." Our overall well-being is significantly shaped by our ability to manage stress[1]. Understanding the effects of stress on health poses an ongoing challenge due to the complex nature of stress and its behavioural components. Previous research has established that high stress levels are directly associated with an increased risk of a variety of diseases and health conditions, including cardiovascular disease, hypertension, stroke, obesity, immune function, and accelerated disease progression. Stress is believed to affect health through two distinct yet interacting pathways: a direct biological pathway (for example, by affecting neuroendocrine and autonomic processes) and an indirect behavioural pathway (for instance, by influencing both habitual and non-habitual health behaviours). These pathways are likely to function in a bi-directional manner, where changes in behaviour can impact biological processes, and changes in biology can influence behaviours that affect health. Over the last twenty-five years, a substantial body of research has examined the relationship between stress and eating behaviour, with a significant number of studies indicating that stress is associated with changes in food intake among children and young adults[2].

Young adults undergo a prolonged transition from adolescence to adulthood[3]. Young adults aged 18-25 are entering a pivotal life transition phase. During this time, many personal, social, and environmental changes take place, such as relocating from home, beginning tertiary education, cohabiting with peers or partners, and starting their careers. This period is characterized by increased instability, where young people often experience a series of romantic relationships and frequent job changes before making long-term decisions [4]. These transitions can lead to unhealthy lifestyle choices, including weight gain, poor dietary habits, and sedentary lifestyle. Worldwide, young men show a higher prevalence of overweight and obesity compared to young women (~18% vs ~17%), with these differences being more pronounced in developed countries (~37% vs ~29%). A particular concern is the rapid increase in weight beginning at age 18, resulting in nearly 60% of males from developed nations being classified as overweight or obese by the ages of 35-39 [5]. The significant changes during this time create instability and uncertainty, posing a notable risk to mental health and cause stress⁽⁶⁾.

Stress levels tend to escalate during young adulthood as individuals are required to adapt to various physical and emotional changes while tackling life challenges [6]. If you are experiencing a lot of mental strain every day, your general health as a young adult is jeopardised. Stress has a huge impact on how we feel emotionally, our feeling of well-being, our behaviors, as well as our mental and physical well-being [7]. There is a strong link between nutrition and mental health in adults, which has been found to vary between individuals with depression and anxiety [8]. When stressed, individuals typically eat not because they are hungry, but as a way to manage their stress⁽⁶⁾. Stress can also affect dietary behaviours, including restraint behaviours, emotional eating, and eating in response to external cues [9].

Stress is related to dietary behaviors and impacts eating patterns, which can lead to overeating or meal-skipping. Overeating can cause obesity, while skipping meals may lead to weight loss, both of which can have significant adverse effects on health. Proper dietary habits are crucial for balanced nutritional intake and are a major determinant of individual health status. Irregular eating habits can disrupt physical health and also influence psychological well-being and emotional stability [6]. In contrast, emotional undereating may serve as a protective factor these influences can cause dysfunctional emotional eating, which is crucial element in the formation of eating disorders [10].

Furthermore, dietary intake has been shown to differ between males and females with mental health disorders. For example, earlier research has indicated that depressed or anxious females consume greater quantities of unhealthy foods than depressed or anxious males [8]. Stress is associated with a reduction in self-efficacy for physical activity, an increase in the consumption of high-fat and high-carbohydrate 'comfort' foods and energy drinks, and a decrease in the intake of healthy foods such as fruits and vegetables. It is important for young adults to understand which foods promote mental health. Skipping meals and following unhealthy eating patterns may harm the mental health of those between 18 and 24 years old [11]. However, there has been limited research conducted among young working adults in India to investigate eating behaviours during stress. Therefore, the objectives of this study were (I) to measure stress (II) to assess dietary habits and (III) to explore relation between stress and dietary habits.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This observational study involved the enrolment of North Indian young adults aged 18 to 35 through an online data collection method. The study's objectives were communicated to participants orally. Informed consent was obtained from those who agreed to participate. A non-probability sampling technique known as snowball sampling was employed to distribute the online questionnaire to a readily available pool of respondents. This approach was chosen to facilitate data collection and maximize the response rate. The sample size was calculated using an online Cochrane sample size calculator, targeting a population size of 1000, with a margin of error of 5% and a confidence level of 95%. According to the sample size formula provided, the minimum recommended sample size was calculated to be 278 from a target population of 1000. An online structured questionnaire was created using Google Forms and distributed to all eligible young adults via Microsoft Teams, email, and WhatsApp. An online structured questionnaire, comprising three parts, was developed using Google

Forms. The first part included questions on socio-demographic data such as age, sex, marital status, place of living, education status, and family monthly income along with Weight, height, and Body Mass Index (BMI) were also included in this part. The second part included questions on dietary habits, such as the frequency of daily meal intake, patterns of skipping breakfast, lunch, and dinner (categorized as usually, occasionally, rarely, and never), as well as fast food consumption and dining out. Stress was assessed in the third part using the Cohen Perceived Stress Scale (PSS).

Measures

Socio-demographic characteristics

Sociodemographic information comprised questions related to sex, age, place of residence, highest educational qualification, employment status (unemployed, self-employed), marital status (married/unmarried), family type (nuclear or joint), and the monthly income of adults was classified as low (1-5 lakh rupees per annum), medium (6-10 lakh rupees per annum), and high (> ₹ 10 lakh). Anthropometric measures Self-reported height (cm) and weight (kg) of participants were noted, and Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated. The World Health Organization (WHO) BMI cut-offs for the Asian adult population were employed to classify adults as: underweight, overweight, or normal weight.

Body Mass Index (Kg/m ²)	Classification
< 18.50	Underweight
18.5 – 24.9	Normal weight
25.0 – 29.9	Overweight
30.0 – 34.9	Obese grade I
35.0 – 39.9	Obese grade II
>40.0	Obese grade III

Measuring dietary habits

The dietary habits segment of the questionnaire used to evaluate the dietary habits (categorized as good, average, and poor) of the participants. The dietary behaviour questionnaire was constructed based on existing relevant literature and questionnaire on young adults eating habits. The questionnaire was prepared in simple and lucid language. It was closed ended questionnaire with given options (usually, occasionally, rarely and never). It was filled by the investigator through the personal interview technique and by subject using a google form. Data was collected regarding meal skipping, the frequency of meals consumed per day, eating out, and the consumption of unhealthy junk food. The dietary habits questionnaire comprises a total of 9 questions, with scoring applied to 8 questions using a 4-point Likert scale. Scores were given to each option like(Never-4,rarely-3,occasionally-2 and for usually-1 and reverse scoring was applied to question regarding taking meal on time as (Never-1,rarely-2,occasionally-3 and for usually-4) .one question not included in scoring was related to the type of diet followed (vegetarian, non-vegetarian, or eggetarian).A higher score indicates better dietary habits. In this study, scores ranging from 0 to 13 points were classified as poor eating habits, 14 to 26 points as average eating habits, and scores above 27 points as good eating habits for analysis. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were established prior to the study with expert review and pilot study.

Assessing level of stress

The stress score used PSS (perceived stress scale) developed by Cohen et al. [12]. and adapted by Lee et al. [13]. Stress was assessed in the third part using a validated 10-item questionnaire that measures how respondents perceive their life situations as stressful, unpredictable, uncontrollable, and

overwhelming. The questions asked individuals about their stress levels over the month prior to being surveyed, using a 4-point rating scale from 0 (never) to 4 (very often) for each item, with items 4, 5, 7, and 8 having their scores reversed. Individual scores were calculated by summing the responses to all 10 items. This results in a total stress score ranging from 0 to 40, where a higher score indicates a higher level of perceived stress. The scores are further divided into three categories of perceived stress: low (0-13), moderate (14-26), and high (27-40). It should be noted that the PSS is not a diagnostic instrument, and thus, there are no cut-offs for identifying stressed individuals. Higher scores correlate with higher perceived stress levels.

Statistical analysis

The collected data were analysed using an IBM SPSS Statistics Software, version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to generate percentages, frequencies, means, standard deviations, and total scores for the Cohen Perceived Stress Scale. Independent-sample T test and one-way ANOVA were employed to compare means related to sociodemographic factors, dietary habits, and stress levels. Karl Pearson correlation was applied to find significant correlations between dietary habits and stress levels. The significance level was defined as ($p < 0.05$)

Results

Participants and sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

The primary analytical sample included 1000 young working adults aged 18 to 35, with their characteristics presented in (Table 1). Most participants were male (52.6%), with the largest age group being those aged 26 to 30 years (43.2%) and 31 to 35 years (41.4%). The highest percentage of participants had postgraduate education (30.8%), and more females achieved the highest doctorate degree (12.6%) compared to males (7.4%). Among the subjects, (46.2%) lived at home, (38.4%) were renting, and (15.4%) lived in hostels or PG accommodations. Among the total participants, (59.4%) were married while (40.6%) were unmarried. A significant majority, (77.4%) lived in nuclear families, while (22.6%) were part of joint families. The highest income group comprised 39.2% of participants, with more males (27.8%) in this category than females (11.4%). Conversely, a larger proportion of females (24.2%) fell into the low-income group compared to males (16.8%), while the total percentage of those in the middle-income group was (19.8%). Most participants (34.4%) had a BMI categorized as overweight, with a higher prevalence among male participants (18.2%) compared to females (16.8%).

The BMI profile of respondents

The BMI profile raised concerns, revealing that (34.4%) of participants were categorized as overweight and (25.4%) as obese, whereas only (27.0%) were able to maintain a normal weight. The presence of unhealthy weight profiles alongside moderate-to-high stress highlights the susceptibility of this age group to lifestyle-related non-communicable diseases (NCDs). This pattern reflects India's current epidemiological transition, where young adults are increasingly engaged in sedentary jobs, irregular work patterns, and imbalanced diets (ICMR-NIN, 2020).

Dietary habit characteristics

Table 2 illustrates the dietary habits distribution among Indian young working adults aged 18–35 years ($n = 1000$), categorized by gender. Among males, (15.2%) reported poor dietary habits with an average score of 10.65 ± 1.59 , while 31.6% exhibited average habits (20.94 ± 3.37) and only (5.8%) reached good dietary habits (28.0 ± 1.05). Conversely, no females were classified as having poor dietary habits. The majority of females (41.0%) demonstrated average habits with a mean score of (21.04 ± 3.34) whereas (6.4%) were categorized under good dietary habits, with a mean score of (28.34 ± 1.08). In summary, the findings reveal that a higher proportion of both males and females fall within the average dietary habit category, while a smaller percentage achieve good dietary practices.

Stress level among young working adults

Stress level among young adults is described in the supplement (Table 3). In a study involving 1000 participants, 526 were identified as males (52.6%) and 474 as females (47.4%). The stress level distribution indicated gender differences. A higher percentage of females reported moderate stress (28.4%) compared to males (22.2%), while males were more commonly found in the high stress category (27.4%) against (14.4%). The incidence of low stress was low in both genders, with males at (3.0%) and females at (4.6%). Across all stress categories, males exhibited consistently higher mean stress scores. In the high stress group, males had a mean score of (32.36 ± 3.22) which was higher than the female mean of (29.97 ± 2.29) . Similarly, in the moderate stress group, males scored (21.53 ± 3.95) while females scored (18.11 ± 4.24) . Even in the low stress category, males had higher mean scores (11.73 ± 2.01) compared to females (8.65 ± 2.32) . Overall, the mean total stress score for males (26.61 ± 7.28) was significantly greater than that of females (20.55 ± 7.66) .

comparison socio-demographic variables and stress

A comparison of socio-demographic variables, including age, income, and gender, with stress is illustrated in the (table 5). The independent sample t-test revealed a significant difference in stress levels based on gender ($p = 0.013$). Males (26.61 ± 7.28) reported considerably higher stress than females (20.79 ± 7.56) . This indicates that males are subjected to greater occupational and lifestyle pressures. Furthermore, a one-way ANOVA showed significant differences in stress scores across various age groups ($F = 18.19, p < 0.001$). The age group of 31–35 years had the highest stress levels (26.00 ± 7.84) , followed by the 18–21 age group (24.0 ± 0.0) , while the lowest stress was found in the 26–30 age group (22.20 ± 7.74) . This pattern suggests that stress tends to increase with age among young working adults. Similarly, income levels had a significant effect on stress ($p < 0.001$). High-income participants reported greater stress (25.87 ± 7.80) compared to those in the middle-income (23.04 ± 7.57) and low-income categories (22.32 ± 7.89) . This indicates that the financial and occupational demands associated with higher income may contribute to increased stress.

comparison socio-demographic variables and dietary habits

comparison socio-demographic variables and dietary habits illustrated in (Table 6). The independent sample t-test revealed a statistically significant gender difference in dietary habits ($p < 0.001$). Females (18.73 ± 3.85) reported markedly higher dietary habit scores compared to males (15.88 ± 5.55) , indicating that women were more likely to adopt healthier eating practices. One-way ANOVA demonstrated significant variation in dietary habits across age groups ($p = 0.005$). The highest dietary scores were observed among young adults aged 26–30 years (17.73 ± 4.68) , followed by the 22–25 years group (17.64 ± 4.58) , while the lowest scores were recorded in the 31–35 years group (16.56 ± 5.45) . This suggests that dietary quality tends to improve in early adulthood but declines slightly with advancing age. Significant differences were also found across income groups ($p < 0.001$). Participants from the middle-income category reported the highest dietary scores (17.90 ± 4.44) , followed closely by the low-income group (17.83 ± 4.66) , while the high-income group had the lowest dietary scores (16.26 ± 5.50) . These findings suggest that higher income may not necessarily translate into healthier food choices, possibly due to lifestyle pressures, urban fast-food consumption, or work-related constraints.

Correlation stress and dietary habits

Pearson's correlation analysis was applied between stress and dietary habits showed in (table 7). The descriptive analysis indicated that participants had a mean stress score of (23.85 ± 7.96) which reflects moderate stress levels. In comparison, the mean score for dietary habits was (17.23 ± 5.02) indicating that dietary practices among young working adults are less than optimal. Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between stress levels and dietary habits ($r = -0.354, p < 0.001$). This finding suggests that higher stress correlates with poorer dietary behaviours in this population. The moderate correlation strength highlights the role of stress as a significant factor influencing dietary choices.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristic of study participants by gender: young adults aged (18-35), n1000

Variables	Male		Female		Total
	Frequency (%)		Frequency (%)		Frequency (%)
Age(years)					
18-21	4(0.4)		0		4(0.4)
22-25	96(9.6)	54(5.4)		150(15.0)	
26-30	222(22.2)		210(21.0)		432(43.2)
31-35	204(20.4)		210(21.0)		414(41.4)
Literacy					
12th	40(4.0)		58(5.8)		98(9.8)
Diploma	116(11.6)		0		116(11.6)
Graduate	198(19.8)		80(8.0)		278(27.8)
Post-graduate	98(9.8)		210(21.0)		308(30.8)
Doctorate	74(7.4)		126(12.6)		200(20.0)
Place of Living					
Home	214(21.4)		248(24.8)		462(46.2)
Rent	238(23.8)		146(14.6)		384(38.4)
Hostel/PG	74(7.4)		80(8.0)		154(15.4)
Marital st					
Married	298(29.8)		296(29.6)		594(59.4)
Unmarried	228(22.8)		178(17.8)		406(40.6)
Type of family					
Nuclear	404(40.4)		370(37.0)		774(77.4)
Joint	122(12.2)		104(10.4)		226(22.6)
Household income					
Low (1-5 Lakh pa)	168(16.8)		242(24.2)		410(41.0)
Middle (6-10 Lakh pa)	80(8.0)		118(11.8)		198(19.8)
High (> 10 Lakh pa)	278(27.8)		114 (11.4)		392(39.2)
BMI					
Underweight	68(6.8)		64(6.4)		132(13.2)
Normal weight	114(11.4)		156(15.6)		270(27.0)
Overweight	182(18.2)		162(16.2)		344(34.4)
Obese	162(16.2)		92(9.2)		254 (25.4)

Data are shown as frequency (%). Underweight:<18.5, normal:18.5-22.9, overweight:23-24.9, obese: ≥25.pa=pen annum

Table 2: Dietary habits: young adults aged (18-35) years n1000

Dietary habits	Male		Female	
	n(%)	Mean ± SD	n(%)	Mean (SD)
Poor	152(15.2)	10.65±1.59	0	0
Average	316(31.6)	20.94±3.37	410(41.0)	21.04±3.34
Good	58(5.8)	28.0±1.05	64(6.4)	28.34±1.08

Data are shown as mean ± SD or number (%), poor score=0-13, average score=14-26, good score=>27

Figure 1: Dietary pattern among young adults aged (18-35) years n1000

Table 3: Stress distributed by gender: young adults aged (18-35) years (n1000)

Stress level	Male		Female	
	n(%)	Mean ± SD	n(%)	Mean (SD)
Low stress	30(3.0)	11.73±2.01	46(4.6)	8.65±2.32
Moderate	222(22.2)	21.53±3.95	284(28.4)	18.11±4.24
High	274(27.4)	32.36±3.22	144(14.4)	29.97±2.29
Total	526(52.6)	26.61±7.28	474(47.4)	20.55 ±7.66

Data are shown as frequency (%), Mean ± SD. Perceived low stress score=0-13, moderate stress score=14-26, high stress score=27-40

Table 4: Comparison mean of stress with sociodemographic variables (age, gender, income), in young adults (n1000) in 2024

Sociodemographic factors	Mean ± SD	F value	t value	sig (p-value)
Gender				
Male female	26.61±7.28	6.24	12.36	**0.013
20.79±7.56				
Age, years				
18-21	24.0±0.00			
22-25	22.71±7.62	18.19		*.000
26-30	22.20±7.74			
31-35	26.00±7.84			
Income, group				
Low	22.32±7.89			
Middle	23.04±7.57	22.06		*.000
High	25.87±7.80			

*One- way ANOVA significant (2 tailed) kept at 0.05, **independent t test significant (2 tailed) kept at 0.05

Table 5: Comparison mean of Dietary habits scores (DHS) with sociodemographic variables (age, gender, income), in young adults (n1000)

Sociodemographic factors	Mean \pm SD	F value	t value	sig (p-value)
Gender				
Male	18.75 \pm 6.24	138.93	-9.98	**0.000
female	22.03 \pm 4.00			
Age, years				
18-21	16.00 \pm 0.0			
22-25	17.64 \pm 4.58	3.57		*.014
26-30	17.73 \pm 4.68			
31-35	16.56 \pm 5.45			
Income, group				
Low	17.83 \pm 4.66			
Middle	17.90 \pm 4.44	13.89		*.000
High	16.26 \pm 5.50			

*One- way ANOVA significant (2 tailed) kept at 0.05, **independent t test significant (2 tailed) kept at 0.05

Supplementary Table 6.: Analysis of Correlation Between Stress Levels and dietary habits in: Indian working young adults n1000

Correlation	p-value	r
Stress level on dietary habits	.000	-.354**

*Karl Pearson Correlation, (r) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7: Descriptive Statistical Test Result stress and dietary habits among young adults (n1000)

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stress Levels	23.85	7.96
Dietary habits	17.23	5.02

Table 8: Distribution of dietary habits among young adults (18-35) according to gender

Dietary habits	Response options	Frequency & Percent		
		Male(n526)	Female(n474)	Total(n1000)
		Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Food habits	Vegetarian	136(13.6)	250(25.0)	386(38.6)
	Non-Vegetarian	306(30.6)	110(11.0)	416(41.6)
	Eggetarian	84(8.40)	114(11.4)	198(19.8)
Meal pattern	1 meal a day	42(4.2)	10(1.0)	52(5.2)
	2 meal a day	144(14.4)	14(1.4)	158(15.8)
	3 meal a day	178(17.8)	270(27.0)	448(44.8)
	4 meal a day	162(16.2)	180(18.0)	342(34.2)
Taking meals on time	Usually	80(8.0)	212(21.2)	292(29.2)
	Occasionally	94(9.4)	148(14.8)	242(24.2)
	Rarely	184(18.4)	106(10.6)	290(29.0)
	Never	168(16.8)	8(0.8)	176(17.6)
Breakfast skipping	Usually	222(22.2)	80(8.0)	302(30.2)
	Occasionally	80(8.0)	112(11.2)	192(19.2)

	Rarely	102(10.2)	126(12.6)	228(22.8)
	Never	122(12.2)	156(15.6)	278(27.8)
Lunch skipping	Usually	62(6.2)	12(1.2)	74(7.4)
	Occasionally	194(19.4)	104(10.4)	298(29.8)
	Rarely	104(10.4)	176(17.6)	280(28.0)
	Never	166(16.6)	182(18.2)	348(34.8)
Dinner skipping	Usually	58(5.8)	4(0.4)	62(6.2)
	Occasionally	124(12.4)	120(12.0)	244(24.4)
	Rarely	156(15.6)	112(11.2)	268(26.8)
	Never	188(18.8)	238(23.8)	426(42.6)
Eating outside food	Usually	272(27.2)	114(11.4)	386(38.6)
	Occasionally	124(12.4)	220(22.0)	344(34.4)
	Rarely	100(10.0)	114(11.4)	214(21.4)
	Never	30(3.0)	26(2.6)	56(5.6)
Prefer junk food	Usually	290(29.0)	212(21.2)	502(50.2)
	Occasionally	150(15.0)	130(13.0)	280(28.0)
	Rarely	34(3.4)	56(5.6)	90(9.0)
	Never	52(5.2)	76(7.6)	128(12.8)
Prefer packed or outside food in place of meal	Usually	220(22.0)	66(6.6)	286(28.6)
	Occasionally	164(16.4)	230(23.0)	394(39.4)
	Rarely	78(7.8)	132(13.2)	210(21.0)
	Never	64(6.4)	46(4.6)	110(11.0)

Discussion

This study assessed the dietary habits and stress levels of Indian young working adults (18–35 years, n= 1000), describing dietary patterns and exploring their associations with sociodemographic characteristics and correlation between stress and dietary habits. The young adult population represents the country's future workforce and eating patterns established during these formative adult years may represent a template for long-term consumption habits and thus disease risk[14]. The analysis of dietary habits among young adults reveals notable gender differences in eating behaviors. A higher proportion of males reported non-vegetarian preferences (30.6%) compared to females (11.0%), whereas vegetarianism was more prevalent among females (25.0%) than males (13.6%). The majority of participants followed a three-meal routine (44.8%), with females (27.0%) surpassing males (17.8%). Four-meal patterns were also reported (34.2%), with a slightly higher share among females (18.0%) compared to males (16.2%), a considerable proportion of males consumed only one (4.2%) or two meals (14.4%) per day, reflecting irregularity in eating frequency. Males showed poorer adherence to timely meals, with 16.8% never eating on time, compared to only 0.8% of females. Conversely, females (21.2%) were more likely than males (8.0%) to usually take meals on time, showing better discipline among women. Breakfast skipping was more common among males, with 22.2% usually skipping compared to (8.0%) of females. Females were more consistent in consuming main meals, while males exhibited greater irregularity. A significant proportion of males (27.2%) usually ate outside food compared to females (11.4%) men are more frequent consumers of restaurant or fast food. Half of the participants (50.2%) reported usually preferring junk food, with males (29.0%) slightly higher than females (21.2%) indicating that unhealthy eating choices are widespread across both genders. Males (22.0%) were more likely than females (6.6%) to usually replace meals with packaged or outside food and shift toward convenience-driven dietary patterns.

These findings indicate that women are more likely to follow healthier dietary practices, which may reflect greater nutritional awareness or sociocultural emphasis on health maintenance among females. Similar gender-based differences have been documented in other Indian and global studies, where men were more prone to irregular eating patterns and processed food consumption (WHO, 2020). Findings highlight that dietary habits among Indian young working adults are significantly influenced by gender, age, and income.

The trend of fast-food consumption and breakfast skipping has been noted to increase during the transition to adulthood, with both behaviors associated with weight gain. Earlier studies demonstrated that those who skip breakfast tend to consume more energy from snacks that are higher in fat, likely due to increased hunger later in the day. This pattern of irregular eating and high snacking among young adults could be attributed to their newfound independence, along with the responsibility of obtaining and preparing food. They may not be sufficiently organized to prepare meals and might have enough financial resources to buy convenient, energy-dense, ready-made foods that are readily available, thus perceived as an easy option [15]. This aligns with evidence linking stress to meal skipping, reliance on fast foods, and emotional eating, which may further exacerbate weight gain and metabolic risks [16].

In this study, the perceived stress of young adults' subjects was 26.61 ± 7.28 in men 20.55 ± 7.66 and in women, 23.85 ± 7.96 in all subjects. From these results, perceived stress seemed higher in male subjects compared female. The present study sought to identify whether retrospective report of dietary habits associated with stress among young working adults. Report of dietary habits was associated with multi factors among young adults including time constrains, living outside home, engaged in carrier activity, lack of availability, and stress. The average and poor dietary pattern observed in young adults who reported stress. Sociodemographic variables further influenced both dietary habits and stress. Age was a significant determinant of stress and dietary behaviors. Participants aged 31–35 years reported the highest stress scores (26.0 ± 7.84), reflecting cumulative family and career responsibilities. In terms of diet, participants aged 22–25 years achieved relatively better scores (17.64 ± 4.58) compared to other age groups ($p = 0.014$). Income also showed a dual impact: participants from middle-income households demonstrated healthier dietary habits (17.90 ± 4.44), while those from high-income groups reported greater stress (25.87 ± 7.80 , $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that financial stability may support better nutrition but also contribute to occupational pressure and psychological burden. The majority of participants reported average dietary practices, with (41.0%) of females and (31.6%) of males falling into this category. Good dietary habits were observed in (6.4%) of females and (5.8%) of males, whereas (15.2%) of males demonstrated poor dietary scores (10.65 ± 1.59). Notably, no females were categorized in the poor dietary group. The mean dietary score was significantly higher among females (22.03 ± 4.00) compared to males (18.75 ± 6.24 , $p < 0.001$).

The results of correlation analysis of stress and dietary habit in young adults showed a significantly negative correlation between stress and dietary pattern. A key finding of the study was the significant inverse correlation between stress and dietary habits ($r = -0.354$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that higher stress levels were associated with poorer dietary quality. The bidirectional nature of this relationship suggests that addressing stress may indirectly improve dietary behaviors and vice versa. Also, results of previous studies supported the results of this study in which it is highly possible for adults with higher stress to have undesirable dietary habits, causing health problems [17-19]. In the previous research, the results showed the correlations among life stress, sleep, anthropometric measurement and nutrient intakes of college students⁽²⁰⁾. Research indicates that approximately 35–40% of individuals increase their food intake, which can consequently lead to weight gain through a chronic positive energy balance when they are under stress. Conversely, the remaining individuals either reduce their food intake or do not change it in response to stress. In contrast, some individuals may decrease their food consumption, which can lead to weight loss through a chronic negative energy balance[2].

Stress related eating may have the potential to significantly contribute to unhealthy eating behaviors. If stress-eating takes place often or even daily, these eating behaviors can result in unhealthy weight change and changes in physiologic measures such as nocturnal levels of insulin, cortisol, and blood levels of total/HDL cholesterol ratio. stress has been linked to unhealthy eating habits and lower diet quality, along with an elevated body mass index (BMI). However, it is only the behavior of maintaining regular meal patterns that showed a significant relationship with lower BMI, all of which effect onset of chronic disease [21]. Stress is associated with dietary behavior, and also affects dietary intake patterns and can induce overeating or meal-skipping. Overeating leads to obesity and meal-skipping can reduce body weight resulting in serious adverse effect on health [16]. Proper dietary

habits are the basics of balanced nutritional intake and a major factor to determine the individual health status. Irregular dietary habits not only disrupt physical health but also can affect psychological condition and emotional stability [22]. Also, in a study of office workers, insufficient sleep caused higher work stress [23]. These results supported the fact that good dietary habits can be an important factor in relieving stress. Such data support our results that the causes of life stress have an association based on the diet quality, anthropometric measurement, and nutrient intake. In conclusion, stress was higher in young adults as dietary habits became undesirable. It is necessary to investigate researches on lifestyle improvement in young age people and to provide nutrition education for them, and individuals also should actively try for accomplishing these goals. These results highlight the importance of customized nutritional intervention and stress management to enhance dietary quality, particularly among young men.

Conclusion

The current investigation highlights significant gender-based differences in dietary habits among young working adults in India. Males were more likely to report preferences for non-vegetarian foods, exhibit irregular meal patterns, frequently skip meals such as breakfast, lunch, or dinner, and show a higher tendency towards junk and takeout food. Females demonstrated a stronger adherence to vegetarian diets, maintained regular three- or four-meal patterns, and exhibited more consistent meal timing, reflecting healthier eating behaviors overall. Despite these variations, the overall findings reveal a concerning prevalence of unhealthy dietary practices across both genders, including high rates of breakfast skipping (30.2%), reliance on outside food (38.6%), and frequent consumption of junk food (50.2%). These behaviors are troubling, given their established links to nutritional deficiencies and long-term risks of obesity and non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Therefore, the results emphasize the urgent need for targeted nutritional awareness and workplace-based interventions aimed at promoting balanced diets, regular meal schedules, and reduced dependence on processed and outside food. Gender-sensitive strategies may further enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives in improving dietary practices among young adults.

Overall, the findings indicate that males tend to engage in more unhealthy eating behaviors, such as frequent meal skipping, greater reliance on junk/outside food, and irregular meal timing. In contrast, females display comparatively healthier patterns, including regular meal consumption and adherence to vegetarian diets. Nonetheless, the prevalence of breakfast skipping, junk food consumption, and reliance on convenience foods across both genders highlights a broader trend toward unhealthy dietary practices in young working adults.

This study shows stress levels are significantly higher among males. Findings emphasize that gender, age, and income are significant socio-demographic determinants of stress among young working adults in India. These findings underscore the importance of implementing targeted stress management interventions that are tailored to demographic characteristics. This study also demonstrates that inverse association between stress and dietary habits highlights the need for integrated interventions that address both mental well-being and nutritional behaviors. Promoting balanced diets, stress management programs, and workplace wellness policies could help mitigate the dual burden of poor nutrition and psychological strain. Future longitudinal and intervention-based research should further explore these relationships to inform sustainable health promotion strategies among India's working youth population. This study suggests a targeted approach that could serve as a foundation for encouraging healthy living and, consequently, preventing obesity in this at-risk age group. Taken together, the data emphasize the urgent need for workplace-centered interventions focusing on stress reduction, dietary education, and promotion of physical activity. Special attention should be directed toward high-risk groups such as males, individuals aged 31–35 years, and those in high-income demanding occupations. Such interventions could help mitigate the dual burden of stress and poor dietary practices, thereby reducing long-term risks of obesity, cardiovascular disease, and other NCDs in India's young workforce.

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Limitation

There are several limitations to consider. This study was cross-sectional, and therefore temporal sequence cannot be established. This study did not reflect objective data of the subjects such as biochemical data or hormonal changes by stress. Therefore, it is suggested to perform a study in the future reflecting health status and objective stress level of the subjects on the basis of biochemical values. Despite these limitations, this study is meaningful in analyzing the stress status according to perceived stress and dietary habits by sex in Thus, the study results will be used as basic data to develop nutrition education programs and nutrition intervention for lifestyle improvement according to sex and stress in young adults. Our study findings align with previous literature that has emphasised the importance dietary habits for good health (1-23). However, we have demonstrated that the relationship between the stress and dietary habits not with biochemical parameters of body.

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